

E- BANKING (BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES IN AN EMERGING ECONOMY)

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ABSTRACT: New Information technology has taken important place in future development of financial services, especially banking sector transition are affected more than any other financial provider groups. Increased use of mobile services and use of internet as new distribution channel for banking transactions and international trading requires more attention towards e-banking security against fraudulent activities. The development and the increasing progress that is being experienced in the Information and Communication Technology have brought about a bunch of changes in almost all facets of life. In the Banking Industry, it has been in the form of E-banking, which is now replacing the traditional banking practice. E-banking has a lot of benefits which add value to customers' satisfaction in terms of better quality of service offerings and at the same time enable the banks gain more competitive advantage over other competitors. This paper discusses challenges in an emerging economy.

KEYWORDS: E- Banking, Information Technology, Customer Satisfaction

1. INTRODUCTION

The economy of most developing countries is cash driven; meaning that monetary transactions are basically made through the exchange of bank notes and coins for goods and services. However, this trend is now giving way to a modern and sophisticated payment system where the currency and notes are converted to data, which are in turn transmitted through the telephone lines and satellite transponders. This is as a result of rapid technological progress and development in the financial market (Ozuru et al. 2010; Johnson, 2005). There is faster delivery of information from the customer and service provider, thus differentiating Internet enabled electronic banking system from the traditional banking operation (Singhal and Padhmanabhan, 2008; Salawu et al. 2007). This transfer process makes money to be carried in information storage medium such as cheques, credit cards, and electronic means than its pure cash form. E-banking has thus become important channel to sell Products and Services; leading to a

paradigm shift in marketing practices, resulting in high performance in the banking industry (Christopher et al. 2006; Brodie et al 2007; Singhal and Padhmanabhan, 2008). The banking industry has been undergoing changes since the mid 1990s, in the form of innovative use of information technology and development in electronic commerce (Kalakota and Whinston, 1996). This development made e-banking pose as a threat to the traditional branch operations, despite the fact that electronic commerce is still developing and is rapidly changing (Harris and Spence, 2002; Turbin et al. 2002). According to Ozuru et al. (2010) "The importance of electronic payment system in any country can never be over emphasized, due to the dramatic transformation in technological advancements that is being experienced by the global financial industry".

2. What is E-banking?

In simple words, e-banking implies provision of banking products and services through electronic delivery channels. Electronic banking has been

around for quite some time in the form of automatic teller machines (ATMs) and telephone transactions. In more recent times, it has been transformed by the internet – a new delivery channel that has facilitated banking transactions for both customers and banks. For customers,

the internet offers faster access, is more convenient and available around the clock irrespective of the customer’s location.

Figure 1

Why E-Banking?

There are not many inventions that have changed the business of banking as quickly as the e-banking revolution. World over banks are reorienting their business strategies towards new opportunities offered by e-banking. E-banking has enabled banks to scale borders, change strategic behavior and thus bring about new possibilities. E-banking has moved real banking behavior closer to neoclassical economic theories of market functioning. Due to the absolute transparency of the market, clients (both business as well as retail) can compare the services of various banks more easily. For instance, on the internet, competitors are only one click away. If clients are not happy with the products, prices or services offered by a particular bank, they are able to change their banking partner much more easily than in the physical or real bank-client relationship. From the banks’ point of view, use of the internet has significantly reduced the physical costs of banking operations. As discussed by Turner (2001), progress in information technology has slashed the costs of processing information, while the internet has facilitated its transmission, thus facilitating change in the very essence of the banking business. Around the

world, electronic banking services, whether delivered online or through other mechanisms, have spread quickly in recent years.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Internet banking, however, is now used as the term for new age banking system (Singhal and Padhmanbhan, 2008). Internet banking is defined as the use of the Internet to deliver banking activities such as funds transfer, paying bills, viewing current and savings account balance, paying mortgages and purchasing financial instruments and certificates of deposits (Singhal and Padhmanbhan, 2008; Ahasanul et al, 2009). Internet banking is also called Online banking, e- payment and e-banking (Ozuru et al, 2010; Singhal and Padhmanbhan, 2008; Beer, 2006; Jun and Cai, 2001; IAMA, 2006). E-payment is described as a means whereby banking businesses are transacted through automated processes and electronic devices such as personal computers, telephones, and fax machines, Internet card payments and other electronic channels (Turban et al, 2006; Ozuru et al, 2010). The electronic communications used in Internet banking includes: Internet, e-mail, e-books, data base and mobile phones (Chaffey et al,

2006). Cell phone banking apart from Internet banking is considered the way of the future (Fisher – French, 2007; Masocha et al, 2011).

In the recent time, the development in technology has affected business organizations in several ways, most especially in terms of management and control; marketing and research; operations and decision making. It is therefore, the vogue that every organization wants to tap the benefits accrue from technology development. In other word, most organizations find means of enjoying the advantages encapsulated in the new technologies (Larpsiri and Speece, 2004; Durkin and Howcroft, 2003; Masocha et al, 2011). There was reduction of cost through substantial improvement in efficiency by business organizations. This resulted in banks diverting their focus towards extensive computerization and electronic operations (Masocha et al, 2011). The electronic delivery of banking service has become ideal for banks in meeting customers' expectations and building close customer relationship (Ching, 2008; Lamb et al, 2002). It is therefore, no doubt that e-banking will definitely overwhelm traditional banking in the near future; since more developing nations seem to direct their focus on building up their infrastructure with specific attention on e-banking, e-commerce and e-learning (Kamel, 2005; Masocha et al, 2011).

Internet banking started with simple functions such as real time access to information about interest rate, checking account balances and computing loan eligibility. However, these services have graduated to online bill payment, transfer of funds between accounts and cash management services for corporate organizations and individuals (Khan et al, 2009; Singhal and Padhmanbhan, 2008). The development experienced in Internet and other global online networks have thus created new commercial opportunities for e-commerce and creation of completely new sets of global and national trading relationships. This consequently, led to the perception that e-banking and e-commerce are now an inevitable aspect of financial services (Harris and Spencer, 2002).

The use of e-banking has brought many benefits amongst which include: there are no barrier limitations; it is convenient; services are offered at minimal cost; it has transformed traditional practices in banking; the only way to stay connected to the customers at any place and any time is through internet applications; it results in high performance in the banking industry through faster delivery of information from the customer and service provider;

customers prefer the use of e-banking because it saves time; it makes possible the use of innovative product or service at a low transaction fees and it encourages queue management which is one of the important dimensions of e-banking service quality (Gonzalez et al, 2008; Singhal and Padhmanbhan, 2008; Brodie et al, 2007; Williamson, 2006; Beer, 2006; Cooper, 1997; IAMAI's, 2006 and Joseph et al, 1999).

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- The primary objective of the research paper is to get the full acquaintance of the internet banking and its benefits.
- To know the challenges in E-banking.

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The primary source of the information in this research study is the secondary data. The available information on internet regarding the E: Banking has been extensively used to complete the dissertation report. All the available Journals, Articles, papers provided necessary information to the group to finalize the research study.

Internet Banking in India

The financial products and services have become available over the Internet, which has thus become an important distribution channel for a number of banks. Banks boost technology investment spending strongly to address revenue, cost and competitiveness concerns. The purpose of present study is to analyze such effects of IB in India, where no rigorous attempts have been undertaken to understand this aspect of the banking business. A study on the Internet users, conducted by Internet and Mobile Association of India (IAMAI), found that about 23% of the online users prefer IB as the banking Channel in India, second to ATM which is preferred by 53%. Out of the 6,365 Internet users sampled, 35% use online banking channels in India.

This shows that a significant number of online users do not use IB, and hence there is a need to understand the reasons for not using it .Until the advent of ATMs, people were unaware and/or not directly affected by the technological revolutions happening in the banking sector. ATMs became the major revelation for customers, since it offered the facility to avoid long queues in front of the cashiers in banks. It also provided them the flexibility of withdrawing money anytime, anywhere . In the study by IAMAI,

it was found that the people are not doing financial transactions on the banks' Internet sites in India because of reasons such as security concerns (43%), preference for face-to-face transactions (39%), lack of knowledge about transferring online (22%), lack of user friendliness (10%), or lack of the facility in the current bank (2%).

Benefits of E-Banking

The main benefit from the bank customers' point of view is significant saving of time by the automation of banking services processing and introduction of an easy maintenance tools for managing customer's money. The main advantages of e-banking for corporate customers are as follows (BankAway! 2001; Gurău, 2002):

- Reduced costs in accessing and using the banking services.
- Increased comfort and timesaving - transactions can be made 24 hours a day, without requiring the physical interaction with the bank.
- Quick and continuous access to information- Corporations will have easier access to information as, they can check on multiple accounts at the click of a button.
- Better cash management- E-banking facilities speed up cash cycle and increases efficiency of business processes as large variety of cash management instruments are available on Internet sites of Estonian banks. For example, it is possible to manage company's short-term cash via Internet banks in Estonia (investments in over-night, short- and long term deposits, in commercial papers, in bonds and equities, in money market funds).
- Reduced costs- This is in terms of the cost of availing and using the various banking products and services.
- Convenience- All the banking transactions can be performed from the comfort of the home or office or from the place a customer wants to.
- Speed - The response of the medium is very fast; therefore customers can actually wait till the last minute before concluding a fund transfer.
- Funds management- Customers can download their history of different accounts and do a "what-if" analysis on their own PC before affecting any transaction on the web. This will lead to better funds management.

7. Challenges in E-Banking

- The ability to adopt global technology to local requirements: An adequate level of infrastructure and human capacity building are required before developing countries can adopt the global technology for their local requirements. For example, the review of the migration plan of Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunications (SWIFT) to the internet shows that to date full migration has not occurred in many developing countries due to the lack of adequate infrastructure, working capital, and required technical expertise. Broadly accepted e-payment systems are another such example. Many corporate and consumers in some developing countries either do not trust or do not have access to the necessary infrastructure to be able to process e-payments.
- The ability to strengthen public support for e-finance: Historically, most e-finance initiatives in developing countries have been the result of cooperative efforts between the private and public sectors. For example, Singapore's successful Trade Net system was a government-sponsored project. If the public sector does not have the necessary means to implement the projects it is essential that cooperative efforts between public and private sectors, along with the multilateral agencies like the World Bank, be developed to facilitate public support for refinance related initiatives.
- E-Banking has created many new challenges for bank management and regulatory and supervisory authorities. They originate not just from increased potential for cross border transactions but also for domestic transactions based on technology applications which raise many security related issues [Hawkins 2002]. The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision's Electronic Banking Group (EBG) (2001) has defined risk management principles for electronic banking. They primarily focus on how to extend, adapt, and tailor the existing risk-management framework to the electronic banking setting. It is necessary to know whether the efforts undertaken by the RBI are sufficient to ensure a reasonable level of security
- Confidentiality, integrity and authentication are very important features of the banking sector and were very successfully managed the world over in pre-internet times. Communication across an

open and thus insecure channel such as the internet might not be the best base for bank-client relations as trust might partially be lost [Grethen 2001].

- Fifth, there are some serious implications of international e-banking. It is a common argument that low transaction costs potentially make it much easier to conduct cross-border banking electronically. For many banks, crossborder operations offer an opportunity to reap economies of scale. But cross-border finance also needs a higher degree of cross-border supervision. Such cooperation may need to extend to similar supervisory rules and disclosure requirements (for efficiency and to avoid regulatory arbitrage) and some harmonizing of legal, accounting and taxation arrangements. The real question here is whether India at the present juncture is adequately prepared to face the consequences of cross border e-banking?
- There is no commercial bank in India, which has exclusively specialized in the small business segment. SMEs in India have generic problems like the inability to provide quality data, to exhibit formal systems and practices and the lack of asset cover. Legal and regulatory compliance has also been inadequate. Traditional drawbacks like asymmetric and nontransparent data and low capital bases continue to characterize their balance sheets. The problem is further compounded due to the preponderance of a large cash economy in this segment. There are many challenges involved in a web-based relationship model for SMEs within India given the current state of regulation [Sushant Kumar 2001].
- The flip side of this technological boom is that electronic banking is not only susceptible to, but may exacerbate, some of the same risks—particularly governance, legal, operational, and reputational—inherent in traditional banking. In addition, it poses new challenges. In response, many national regulators have already modified their regulations to achieve their main objectives: ensuring the safety and soundness of the domestic banking system, promoting market discipline, and protecting customer rights and the public trust in the banking system.
- New methods for conducting transactions, new instruments, and new service providers will require legal definition, recognition, and permission. For example, it will be essential to define an electronic signature and give it the

same legal status as the handwritten signature. Existing legal definitions and permissions—such as the legal definition of a bank and the concept of a national border—will also need to be rethought.

8. CONCLUSIONS

The banking industry has been a leader in the e-business world in recent years. The e-banking revolution has fundamentally changed the business of banking by scaling borders and bringing about new opportunities. In India also, it has strongly impacted the strategic business considerations for banks by significantly cutting down costs of delivery and transactions. It must be noted, however, that while e-banking provides many benefits to customers and banks, it also aggravates traditional banking risks. Compared to developed countries, developing countries face many impediments that affect the successful implementation of e-banking initiatives. One of the benefits that banks experience when using e-banking is increased customer satisfaction. This due to that customers may access their accounts whenever, from anywhere, and they get involved more, this creating relationships with banks. Banks should provide their customers with convenience, meaning offering service through several distribution channels (ATM, Internet, physical branches) and have more functions available online. Other benefits are expanded product offerings and extended geographic reach. With all these benefits banks can obtain success on the financial market. But e-banking is a difficult business and banks face a lot of challenges.

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